

Comparison of Singular Value Decomposition and Principal Component Analysis applied to Hyperspectral Imaging of Biofilm

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Abstract: Different degrees of bacterial attachment to various surface morphologies observed by Hyperspectral Imaging Method are studied. Fore-ground and back-ground distinction performed by Singular Value Decomposition and Principal Component Analysis is also discussed.

Introduction

Bacterial contamination on medical device surfaces or biofilm formation in particular, has universally become one of the most common complications to public health. Therefore it is essential to monitor and investigate its configuration on medical devices to prevent cross contamination as well as to ease economic losses and public health risks. Hyperspectral Imaging (HSI) method has demonstrated its capability as an effective technique in biomedical research to distinguish bacterial contaminants on various surface scales among other techniques such as confocal laser scanning microscopy [1], optical coherence tomography [2], and low-coherence interferometry [3]. In this study, HSI system based on spectrograph was utilized for the investigation of different biofilm growth on different medical surface. In addition, observation and comparison between Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) were performed for low expression pattern detection.

Experiments and Discussion

Our HSI system setup contains an imaging spectrograph attached to an electron multiplying charge-couple device (emCCD) camera coupled with an objective lens (Headwall's Hyperspec[®] VIS, Massachusetts). The spectrograph with a 25 μ m-by-18mm slit separates incoming light into specific wavelength spectrum ranging from 380 nm to 825 nm. The system's lighting component comprises of a pair of intensity-adjustable 150Watt quartz halogen lights (Fiber-LiteA-241, Dolan-Jenner Industries, Massachusetts) for reflectance measurement and two UV-A lamps (Spectroline[®] XX15A 365nm, Spectronics Corporation, New York) for fluorescence excitation. Placement angles of all lamps were adjusted to achieve the most uniform light distribution on the tested sample without specular reflection. A linear stepper motor stage (XSlide[™] slide assembly, VELMEX, Inc., New York) was used to facilitate line-by-line imaging acquisition. The schematic of the HSI system is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the HSI system used in this study.

Detection and monitoring of *Escherichia coli* growth on multi-purpose stainless steel (SS) coupon using the microscopic HSI system was reported elsewhere [4]. *E. coli* colony is successfully distinguished from SS background surface. However, biofilm matrix with its weak expression pattern provided a lower resolution and less useful information to discern from metallic background surface. Therefore, it is necessary to differentiate low profile body from the unwanted surface. In this study we demonstrate the comparison of PCA and SVD for low intensity signature detection. Random noise distribution is introduced to the signature region. The interested wavelengths are at 691.4 nm, 696.1 nm, 700.8 nm, 794.3 nm and from 677.4 nm to 724.1 nm. According to Fig. 2, it is noticeable that PCA performs better reconstructed image at lower light profile than SVD since PCA considers mean of the data set while SVD the raw data set.

Fig. 2. Contaminant study region **(a)** Mean noised image; **(b)** First PCA; **(c)** First SVD

Based on the capability to differentiate low profile body using SVD and PCA, additional verification of biofilm formation mechanism on different surface morphologies were performed using different surface finishes of stainless steel (SS) samples. The hypothesis is that different surface morphologies will bring into different formation of biofilm from changes in bacterial adhesion to the exposed surface, under the same conditions of bacterial strain and nutrient environment property. SS coupons (type 304, McMASTER-CARR, California) utilized in this study contained 18-20% Chromium and 8-12% Nickel. Unpolished, mirror-liked, fine grain-line brushed and coarse grain-line brushed finishes were induced on coupon surfaces. Fig. 3 indicates spectral differences of four SS morphologies from the translation table background surface. In addition, the mirror-liked surface reflects most of the incoming light away from the HSI camera while fine grain-line brushed morphology scatters the most. However, spectra of all four morphologies stay unchanged due to the same material property. In order to observe the effects of surface morphology on biofilm pattern, further studies focused on monitoring biofilm configuration on these four different metallic planes will be discussed in this study report. Distinctions of biofilm configuration with various light profiles on different metallic surfaces employed by SVD and PCA will also be discussed.

Fig. 3. **(a)** HSI of four different SS surface morphologies at 700nm; **(b)** Spectra of four tested surfaces and the background. Yellow region is the contaminant study region in the first experiment

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have successfully detected a contaminant on metallic surface. The demonstrated HSI system setups can be utilized not only in laboratories but also in field environment as a reliable modality to detect contaminants on medical devices. Further investigations on the mechanism behind the distinctive biofilm growth on different surface morphologies observed by HSI system setups will be studied, encouraging the efficiency of the detection device as well as finding of a safe and pathogen-free material for clinical application.

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